

Prerequisites to Increase the Purchase Intent for a Socially Responsible Company – Development of a Scale

Tutku Eker Iscioglu

Abstract—Increasing attention has been given in academia to the concept of corporate social responsibility. Also, the number of companies that undertake social responsibility initiatives has been boosting day by day since behaving in a socially responsible manner brings a lot to the companies. Literature provides various benefits of social responsibility and under which situations these benefits could be realized. However, most of these studies focus on one aspect of the consequences of behaving in a socially responsible manner and there is no study that unifies the conditions that a company should fulfill to make customers prefer its brand. This study aims to fill this gap. More specifically, the purpose of this study is to identify the conditions that a socially responsible company should fulfill in order to attract customers. To this end, a scale is developed and its reliability and validity is assessed through the method of Multitrait-Multimethod Matrix.

Keywords—Consumers, Corporate Social Responsibility, Multitrait-Multimethod Matrix, Scale Development.

I. INTRODUCTION

CORPORATE social responsibility is defined as the obligation of the corporate decision makers to take action that protects and improves the welfare of the society as a whole, along with their own interests [1]. Being socially responsible brings lots of benefits to the companies.

As it has been argued, socially responsible activities increases sales and customer loyalty, improves financial performance, enhances corporate reputation and brand image, increases ability to attract and retain employees, and fosters employee morale and motivation [2]. Obviously, to focus on all of these benefits of social responsibility initiatives in one study is impossible. Therefore, one of the outcomes of being a socially responsible company – increased sales – is the focus of this study. In other words, company-specific conditions that are needed to be fulfilled in order to increase purchase intention from a socially responsible company are examined.

More specifically, the aim of this study is to develop a proper scale which intends to measure the extent to which consumers demand company-specific conditions to be fulfilled in order to purchase from a socially responsible company.

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Therefore, in the first part of this study, literature was reviewed to identify the conceptual definitions of corporate social responsibility, effects of socially responsible activities on consumers and the conditions that are required by socially responsible companies in order to make their initiatives increase the purchase intention for their own brands. In addition to tracking literature to realize the aim of this study, four focus groups were also carried out in order to develop the intended scale. Therefore, following the first part, research methodology is presented along with research objectives, data collection method, sampling, data analysis, and the assessment of face validity and inter-judge reliability. In the final section of the study, the phases of measurement and scale development were described one by one and especially the assessment of construct validity by the usage of Multitrait-Multimethod Matrix was revealed.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Conceptual Definitions of Corporate Social Responsibility

Interest in understanding the issue of corporate responsibility has emerged during 1950s [3] and attracted the attention of numerous scholars examining the nature of corporate social responsibilities [4]. As corporate social responsibility (labeled CSR hereafter) has become a popular issue to investigate, the literature has revealed an abundance of papers that focused on the topic and in most of all these works authors attempted to define CSR with their own point of views, resulting in various definitions of the term. Moreover, different terminologies were also used to name CSR construct.

Reference [3] provided the first definition of CSR and asserted that businesses have the responsibility to “pursue those politics, to make those decisions, or to follow those lines of actions which are desirable in terms of the objectives and values of our society” (p.6). On the other hand, it is also argued that business is required only to maximize profits within the boundaries of the law and minimal ethical constraints [5]. Similarly, the idea that the only responsibility of corporations is to increase profits by legal means had gained wide acceptance [6].

Even though, such alternative perspectives have emerged about the definition of CSR, the construct has traditionally been conceptualized broadly as the obligation of the corporate decision makers to take action that protects and improves the welfare of the society as a whole, along with their own

interests [1]. A more specific conceptualization of CSR is generated where it is suggested that businesses have four main responsibilities: economic, legal, ethical and philanthropic [7]. Economic responsibilities include performing in a manner consistent with maximizing earnings per share, being as profitable as possible, maintaining a strong competitive position and high level of operating efficiency [8]. Legal responsibilities are defined as obeying or complying with the law [7]. The ethical domain of CSR is defined as embracing those standards, norms or expectations that reflect a concern for what consumers, employees, shareholders, and the community regard as fair, just, or in keeping with the respect or the protection of shareholders' moral rights [8]. And finally, philanthropic responsibilities reflect the common desire to see business get actively involved in the betterment of society [7]-[8]. In order to illustrate the components of his CSR definition, Carroll also incorporated his four-domain categorization into a "Pyramid of CSR" [8], which is presented in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 Carroll's Pyramid of Corporate Social Responsibility

Considering the limitations of this model, an alternative approach to the conceptualization of CSR is provided and called the three-domain model of CSR [9]. Fig. 2 illustrates the three-domain model of CSR. As can be noticed, the fourth domain of Carroll's conceptualization, the philanthropic responsibilities, is not depicted in this new model, the reason being that it may be inaccurate or misnomer to call such activities "responsibilities" due to their voluntary or discretionary nature [10]. Therefore, philanthropy is not considered a duty or social responsibility of business, but something that is merely desirable or beyond what duty requires [9]. Even though there is no separate philanthropic category, it is subsumed within the economic and/or ethical spheres. It is considered that this treatment more appropriately depicts the placement of philanthropy, particularly for business ethics applications and that this new model more completely and accurately portrays the relationships between the central CSR domains: economic, legal, and ethical.

Fig. 2 Three-Domain Model of Corporate Social Responsibility

However, in this study it is believed that philanthropy should be considered one of the separate responsibilities of the corporations. A socially responsible company should have concerns beyond short-term profitability and it should contribute to the well being of the society at large [11]. Therefore, this paper adapts the definition of CSR as a company's commitment to minimizing and eliminating any harmful effects and maximizing its long-run beneficial impact on society [12]. More specifically, in this paper CSR is accepted as fulfilling economic responsibilities while at the same time obeying laws, behaving ethically and initiating philanthropic actions. As a subset of philanthropic actions, cause-related marketing, the linkage of a brand with a particular "good cause" service or charitable organization [13], is taken into consideration in this study.

B. Effects of Socially Responsible Actions on Consumers

Today, companies undertake various CSR initiatives, such as corporate philanthropy associated with education, environment, health, safety, arts and culture, cause-related marketing, minority support programs, and socially responsible employment and manufacturing practices, because of the belief among business leaders that it is an economic imperative in today's national and global marketplace [14]. The benefits of these CSR activities for the corporations include greater employee morale, strengthened employee commitment and productivity, enhanced corporate image and reputation, increased sales and profitability, and customer loyalty [2]- [15]- [16]. It is indicated that cause-related marketing has grown to become a widely accepted business practice as it has simultaneously evolved from a short-term sales-enhancement tactic to a means for improving brand equity and corporate image [17]. However, the belief that CSR initiatives have an impact on consumers have not yet fully supported since many financial payoffs from CSR takes time to materialize [18]. Yet, increasing number of scholars unite on the same notion that a company's CSR initiatives has a positive relationship with consumers' attitudes toward that company and its products [19]- [20]- [18]- [14].

Reference [19] found that high CSR leads to higher evaluation of the company than low CSR, and this evaluation also influences the evaluation of the company's product. In another study, it is argued that consumers are likely to identify with a company that offers them a positive and meaningful

social identity [14]. When consumers personally support the social issues that the company targets (support for the CSR domain), they are likely to see greater congruence between themselves and the company, becoming more likely to be loyal to those companies, promote them to others, and be resilient to negative information about them [21]. Extending these arguments, it is also suggested that CSR may add value to a product since many American consumers value CSR and may use it as a purchasing criterion even when there is not a product parity situation [18]. Nevertheless, it should not be forgotten that responses to CSR are dependent on consumers having valid information about the company [18].

In another study it is found that 49 % of 225 people believe a firm's support of a cause had been a primary reason for them to purchase a product, and 54 % said that they are likely to be influenced to try to a new brand in the future as a result of a cause-related promotion [20]. In another research, it is found that customers would also pay higher prices for an ethical company's products [23].

Other than academic studies, marketplace polls also reveal consumer attitudes to CSR actions. A worldwide survey conducted in 1999 revealed that two-thirds of consumers surveyed wanted companies to contribute to broader societal goals [24]. Reference [25] indicates that, each year since 1993 at least 80% of those surveyed reported having a more positive image of a firm if it offers support to a cause they care about. Moreover, in the case of quality, price and convenience equality, two-thirds or more of the sample said they are likely to switch brands or retailers to those participating in cause-related marketing.

As can be realized, literature and survey results provide abundance of studies indicating that consumers appreciate CSR initiatives and these initiatives lead consumers to favorable attitude and word of mouth, purchase intention and even brand loyalty.

C. Under which Conditions does CSR Affect Purchase Intention?

Reference [25] revealed that, majority of the consumers want to purchase from socially responsible companies when price, quality and convenience of a product are equal with those of others. Yet, it should be acknowledged that consumers first need to become aware of a firm's level of social responsibility before CSR can impact their purchasing [20].

Another condition to fulfill in order to attract consumers with CSR initiatives appears to be the selection of the right cause. Consumers' reactions to a retailer's cause-related marketing efforts not only vary with the type of cause and the retailer's precise role in it but also are reflected in consumers' attributions regarding their own motivations and that of the retailer [26]. Reference [20] also states that when CSR has been experimentally communicated by means other than advertising and when the level of social responsibility has been described as being more extensive than making donation to one cause, the effects of CSR have been more strikingly positive. It is also supported that a high level of CSR leads to a

higher level of purchase intent than a low level of CSR [18]. Considering that there is a lack of knowledge about when, how and for whom specific CSR initiatives work, a study was undertaken and findings implicated that both company-specific factors, such as the CSR issues a company chooses to focus on and the quality of its products, and consumer-specific factors, such as consumers' personal support for the CSR issues and their general beliefs about CSR are key moderators of their responses to CSR [14].

To summarize, past research about under which conditions CSR affect the purchase intention of consumers show that, provision of product and price equality, dissemination of information about the CSR initiatives both through advertisements and other promotion tools, the choice of a right CSR initiative and high level of contribution to a cause are the prerequisites that companies need to fulfill if they perceive CSR initiatives to have positive affect on their profitability. Other than company-specific elements, there are also consumer-specific elements that affect the purchase intention. However, the focus of this study is on company-specific dimensions and therefore consumer related elements are not taken into consideration. Overall dimensions and elements that emerge from literature and that build up the purchase intention for socially responsible companies are presented in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3 Theoretical Framework for the Dimensions and Elements of Purchase-Intention from a Socially Responsible Company

Previous research mostly attempted to understand consumers' attitudes and their purchase intention through qualitative studies with the aim of gaining a deeper understanding of the phenomena. Moreover, most of these scholars studied or found out one or, at most, two types of conditions that consumers seek, i.e. only when price and quality are equal, only when a cause is important to the consumers, etc. Hence, there is a lack of a unified scale that attempts to measure which conditions are more important for consumers and also to what extent consumers demand more conditions to be fulfilled in order to purchase from a socially responsible company.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A. Research Objectives

The basic rationale behind this study stems from the fact that, although the concept of CSR has received considerable attention by many corporations and scholars, there is a paucity of studies on developing an overall understanding of motives that influence consumers' purchase intention from a socially responsible company. Also in literature, there is a lack of a scale that attempts to measure which company provided conditions are mostly preferred by consumers to purchase from a socially responsible company and hence, the extent of the level that consumers seek for such company-specific conditions. More specifically, the objectives of this study are:

- To identify the motives that lead consumers to purchase from a socially responsible company
- To develop a scale that measures to what extent consumers demand more company-specific conditions
- To assess the reliability and validity of the developed scale

B. Data Collection

With the aim of fulfilling the first objective of this study, one of the data collection methods of qualitative research, namely focus group interviews were utilized. Since focus group interviews help to develop a deeper understanding of respondents' feelings, motives, desires and perceptions, and aid the surfacing of emotional responses as a result of group dynamics (Morgan, 1998), it was accepted as the best applicable method for this study. Interviews were semi-structured because such interviews provide some structure to the interview process while encouraging respondents to freely discuss the phenomenon of interest in their own words [27] and allowing the moderator to probe thoughts as needed [28]. Therefore, it was determined that semi-structured interviews should be used to discover various thoughts and motives that consumers have while purchasing from a socially responsible company.

Four focus group interviews were undertaken ranging durations from one hour to an hour and a half. Discussions were tape recorded and then transcribed. The moderator was the researcher of this study. Discussions were carried out in home settings of some of the respondents and most respondents knew each other. The characteristics of each group will be mentioned in the next section.

An interview guide, where questions flow from general to more specific, was prepared. An academician was consulted, who has studied CSR and thus, is knowledgeable about the issue at hand, for the selection and sequence of questions. Following the forming of questions, a pilot study was conducted with three respondents, who are teaching assistants at Istanbul Bilgi University. Consistent with their suggestions, two questions were modified and made clearer.

In each group, discussions started with a general question of which criteria respondents take into account while purchasing. Unfortunately, in none of the groups company's CSR actions were stated as a criterion for purchase. Following the initial question, respondents were showed eight cards where in each

of them one purchase criterion, such as price, quality, function, company's CSR actions etc., was written. Some respondents did not know what CSR means, therefore, a definition of CSR was provided later on. Then, respondents were asked to put in order all these cards from most preferred purchase criterion to least preferred. Again unfortunately, company's CSR actions were put in the last place in all groups, indicating that most respondents do not consider this criterion as a high influencer of their purchase intention. After understanding the purchase criteria that consumers consider, discussions were moved to the identification of conditions that respondents would like to see in order to purchase from a socially responsible company. Therefore, respondents were asked to indicate the conditions that the company has to fulfill in order to make consumers prefer it. As the discussion got deeper, more specific questions were asked to probe whether there are conditions different from what is stated in literature.

C. Sample

Convenience and snowball sampling methods were used to form four groups, in which a total of 34 respondents participated. Majority of the respondents were the acquaintances of the researcher, but in order to increase the group size some respondents were asked to indicate additional respondents. Groups were formed on the basis of age, socio-economic status and education. Even though demographic characteristics were not fully supported to be an indicator of a purchase intention from a socially responsible company, in this research groups were divided on the basis of age (between 18-30 and above 31). Additionally, respondents were high school or university graduates, and belonged to medium and high socio-economic status groups. Two of the focus groups were carried out in İzmir, third biggest city of Turkey. The remaining two groups were conducted in Istanbul. The selection of these two cities is only related with the purpose of being more convenient. The groups are indicated more specifically in Table I.

TABLE I
 PROFILE OF RESPONDENTS

	Place	Age	Number of Respondents
Group 1	İzmir	18-30	8 (4 men, 4 women)
Group 2	İzmir	31>	9 (3 men, 6 women)
Group 3	İstanbul	18-30	8 (3 men, 5 women)
Group 4	İstanbul	31>	9 (3 men, 6 women)

D. Data Analysis

The researcher analyzed and interpreted the interview transcripts by the method of content analysis. Initially, transcripts were read after and after by the researcher to extract company-specific elements or items that were indicated by the literature. All the elements stated by literature also emerged in this study. Later on, the researcher looked for thoughts that had not been specified by the literature but expressed by some of the respondents. Twelve additional items, other than those stated in the literature, emerged from the focus groups. All the items that were mentioned in four of

the focus groups are presented in Table II from most frequent to least.

TABLE II
ITEMS DETERMINING THE CONDITIONS THOSE CONSUMERS SEEK WHILE PURCHASING FROM A SOCIALLY RESPONSIBLE COMPANY

Item Number	Item Name	Frequency
1	No bad behavior in the past (FG) ¹	34
2	Company's trust in the eyes of consumers (FG)	34
3	The money collected from the consumers should be spent for the cause only (FG)	32
4	Behaving socially responsible for a long time (FG)	29
5	Announcing the results of its socially responsible activities (FG)	27
6	Well-known company (FG)	26
7	Being audited by another company for its socially responsible behaviors (FG)	26
8	The cause that the company supports is to be of consumers' concern	24
9	Similar product features with other brands	24
10	Similar price with other brands	23
11	Well-known brand (FG)	23
12	Selling a convenience good (FG)	21
13	Being a large size company (FG)	19
14	No profit aim from the support of the cause (FG)	19
15	Being convenient	18
16	High contribution to the cause	16
17	Communication of the cause with tools other than advertisements	14
18	Selling a shopping good (FG)	5

IV. MEASUREMENT AND SCALE DEVELOPMENT

A. Adjusted Theoretical Framework

The dimensions and elements, which shape the purchase intention of consumers from a socially responsible company, have been extracted from the literature and illustrated in Fig. 3. Whereas in Fig. 4, a new dimension (trust) and its five elements are presented together with the already existing dimensions and elements. There is also two additional elements in the previously called "3Ps" dimension, which incorporated the elements of "equal price", "equal quality", and "equal convenience". However, it had emerged from the focus groups that respondents also want to purchase from a socially responsible company if its product brand is well known to them. In other words, the company also needs to communicate its brand to the consumers so that its awareness increases, which in return feeds the purchase intention of consumers from this socially responsible company. That is why this last element has been titled as the "communication of the product", and hence, the name of the "3Ps" dimension has changed to "4Ps" dimension. Moreover, the product type appears to be another element that has an influence on consumers while purchasing from a socially responsible company. As indicated by some of the respondents, it is easier to purchase from a convenience goods seller if it is socially responsible. On the other hand, the impact of CSR activities diminishes for a shopping good producer. Since the product

type is also related with one of the Ps of 4Ps paradigm, this last element is incorporated into the dimension of 4Ps.

Fig. 4 Adjusted Theoretical Framework of the Dimensions and Elements of Purchase-Intention from A Socially Responsible Company

B. Operational Definitions

Eighteen items and their variable names, dimensions they belong to and their sources are indicated in Table III. All items start with the statement of "I purchase from a socially responsible company ..."

C. Assessment of Face Validity and Inter-Judge Reliability

A total of 18 items were generated as a result of the search of literature and the analysis of focus groups. As stated previously, literature provided 2 dimensions, however, additional elements that emerged from the focus groups were not related with neither of these dimensions. Therefore, the researcher categorized new elements under a different dimension and called it "overall trust that the company created" (In short, "trust").

Initially an attempt was made to assess the face validity of conditions to increase purchase intention from a socially responsible company scale (labeled CIPISRC Scale hereafter). Face validity refers to scale items appearing to measure the construct of interest [29]. The assessment of the face validity of CIPISRC Scale was carried out by asking two judges, one of whom is an academician and the other is a teaching assistant at Istanbul Bilgi University and both of them are knowledgeable about CSR issues, what they thought CIPISRC Scale was measuring. The responses included "decision criteria to purchase from socially responsible companies" and "determinants of buying from companies undertaking CSR". Thus, the scale items seem to reflect the construct CIPISRC, providing evidence for face validity.

¹ Elements that emerged from this study are indicated with FG in parentheses.

TABLE III
OPERATIONALIZATION OF THE VARIABLES IN THE CONDITIONS TO INCREASE
PURCHASE INTENTION SCALE

Variable Name	Statement	Dimension	Source
q1a ²	... as long as the money I spend for the product really goes to the cause	Trust	Researcher
q2a	... even the price of the product is not similar to those of other brands (R) ³	4Ps	Sen and Bhattacharya (2001)
q3a	... as long as the brand is the one I know	4Ps	Researcher
q4a	... as long as its product has equal convenience with those of others	4Ps	Cone/Roper Cause Related Trends Report (1999)
q5a	... even the company has bad past behavior (illegal operations, child labor, etc.) in the past (R)	Trust	Researcher
q6a	... as long as its product features are the same with those of other brands	4Ps	Sen and Bhattacharya (2001)
q7a	... as long as the cause it supports is important to me	Cause	Bhattacharya and Sen, (2003); Ellen et al. (2000)
q8a	... as long as the company is a large size company	Trust	Researcher
q9a	... even the company undertakes CSR just for profit (R)	Trust	Researcher
q10a	... as long as the product it sells is a convenience good (food, beverages, detergents etc.)	4Ps	Researcher
q11a	... as long as I trust the company	Trust	Researcher
q12a	... as long as the consequences of the company's support is announced to the public	Cause	Researcher
q13a	... even the company is not the one I know (R)	Trust	Researcher
q14a	... as long as the company is audited for its socially responsible undertakings	Trust	Researcher
q15a	... as long as the product it sells is a shopping good (TV set, refrigerator, furniture etc.)	4Ps	Researcher
q16a	... even the support of the company to the cause is low (R)	Cause	Mohr et al. (2001); Mohr and Webb (2005)
q17a	... as long as the company undertakes CSR activities for a long time	Cause	Researcher
q18a	... as long as the company communicates its support to the cause by tools other than advertisements	Cause	Mohr et al. (2001)

In order to assess inter-judge reliability, the items listed in Table III are coded into three dimensions by the same two judges mentioned above. The coding of two judges agreed on 16 items out of 18 and according to the formula below reliability is found to be 94%:

$$\text{Reliability} = \frac{N * (\text{average agreement})}{1 + [(N-1) * (\text{average agreement})]} = \frac{2 * 0,888}{1 + (1 * 0,888)} = 94,16\%$$

Where;

N= the number of judges

$$\text{Average agreement} = \frac{\text{number of agreed items}}{\text{total number of items}}$$

Since it is expected that the coding reliability should be above 85%, the result of 94,16% indicates that the coding reliability is high in this research. However, the assessment of the significance of this result is also needed. Therefore, Z-test is carried out as follows:

$$Z = \frac{k - E_k}{\sqrt{N * P(1-P)}} = \frac{16 - (18 * 1/3)}{\sqrt{(18 * 1/3) * (2/3)}} = 6,13$$

Where;

k=Number of agreed items

Ek=Expected number of matches

N=Total number of items

P=The probability of one dimension

Since 6.13 is higher than 2.33, which is the Z-score of an alpha of 0.01, it is concluded that the inter coder reliability of 94.16% is statistically significant. In other words, the probability that the allocation of 18 items into same categories is not attributable to a chance factor.

D. The Questionnaire

As revealed previously, consumers first need to become aware of a firm's level of social responsibility before CSR can impact their purchasing [20]. Keeping this in mind, a little information about an unidentified company operating in a consumer goods market, having socially responsible behaviors and undertaking cause-related marketing was put in the questionnaire, so that respondents could answer by referring to that company. Also, the definition of CSR was provided while mentioning about the actions of this unidentified company. Later on, the items displayed in Table III were constructed into the questionnaire. In the first questionnaire these items were measured with a ratio scale, where the respondents were asked to reveal their thoughts to a statement by assigning a number between 0-100. In order to assess the scale's construct validity with multi-trait multi-method matrix, a second questionnaire was prepared with the same items but this time by using a 7-point interval (Likert) scale, where 1= I strongly disagree, 7=I strongly agree (One of the questionnaires is in the Appendix). In the second questionnaire the items were sorted different from the first one so that respondents would not need to remember their answers to each item in the first

² "a" represents the items that were asked with ratio scale.

³ Reverse coded items are indicate with (R)

questionnaire. Respondents who score high from this scale are considered to be more condition seekers in order to purchase from a socially responsible company. The overview of the two questionnaires with the items' numbers and their dimensions are presented in Table IV.

TABLE IV
 OVERVIEW OF THE TWO QUESTIONNAIRES

	Questionnaire 1		Questionnaire 2	
Dimension	Item No.	Scale	Item No.	Scale
4Ps	2,3,4,6,10,15	Ratio	1,4,5,9,11,15	Interval
Cause	7,12,16,17,18		3,10,16,17,18	
Trust	1,5,8,9,11,13,14		2,6,7,8,12,13,14	

No demographic questions were asked to the respondents since the aim of this research is to assess the construct validity of the scale, not to achieve descriptive information. However, in order compare the two questionnaires later on and thus, to assess the correlation between the traits and the methods, respondents were asked to provide their names by assuring them that their answers will not be judged by considering to whom answers belong to. If they still hesitated to reveal their names, then they were asked to make up a nickname for themselves.

Before sending questionnaires to the respondents, a pilot study with three of the teaching assistants at Istanbul Bilgi University was conducted in order to assess their understanding of the statements in two of the questionnaires. Minor changes with the wording of some statements were made taking into consideration of the suggestions of these three teaching assistants.

E. Sampling and Data Collection

Data was collected through the usage of convenience and snowball sampling methods. The researcher gave the first questionnaire initially to 15 academic and administrative personnel of Istanbul Bilgi University. Then, the same questionnaire was sent to 24 acquaintances of the researcher via e-mail and each acquaintance was asked to send the questionnaire to one more person. A total of 46 questionnaires were obtained back, however 44 of them were eligible to use for further analyses. After ten days, the second questionnaire was given and sent to the same respondents. However, 39 of the respondents filled out the second questionnaire, and 38 of them were appropriate to use. Therefore, the sample consisted of 38 respondents. The questionnaires that belong to the same respondent were put together so that the data of the two questionnaires could be entered in the same row of the SPSS worksheet.

F. Reliability Analyses and Scale Purification

Data analysis was carried out by using SPSS. Reference [30] states that, there are three basic methods for assessing the reliability of a measurement scale: test-retest, internal consistency and alternative forms. In this study, reliability

analyses were conducted to assess the internal consistency of each dimension and thus, to purify items if necessary.

One of the mostly preferred forms of internal reliability, Cronbach's Coefficient Alpha, is used in this study. Since all items are expected to have high contribution to the dimension they belong to, none of them should be deleted unless reliability coefficient increases considerably afterwards. As can be noticed from Table V, no items in cause and trust dimensions were deleted from the first questionnaire. However, there is a deletion in the 4Ps dimension, since Cronbach's Alpha increased from 0.683 to 0.836 after the deletion.

TABLE V
 ASSESSMENT OF THE RELIABILITY ANALYSIS OF QUESTIONNAIRE 1 (RATIO SCALE)

Dimension Name	Reliability Before Deletions	Reliability After Deletions
4Ps	0.683	0.836
Cause	0.635	0.635
Trust	0.752	0.752

Two items had to be deleted from 4Ps dimension and these items are;

q10a: I purchase from a socially responsible company as long as the product it sells is a convenience good (food, beverages, detergents etc.)

q15a: I purchase from a socially responsible company as long as the product it sells is a shopping good (TV set, refrigerator, furniture etc.)

Most probably what is meant by these statements could not be understood clearly by the respondents, even though during pilot studies no problem was encountered regarding these two items. In focus group discussions, majority of the respondents claimed that it would be easier for them to purchase from a convenience good producer when it is socially responsible. The reason being that these products are frequently purchased therefore there is not much a need of making comparisons between the brands all the time. On the other hand, it gets harder to purchase from a shopping good producer even if it undertakes CSR activities, because this time there is a need to compare the brands on the basis of quality, functions, price, payment alternatives, after sale services etc. Since these products are not purchased frequently, consumers consider selecting the one that fulfills their needs and wants mostly and therefore, do not consider CSR activities as a purchase criterion. Therefore, to make these two statements clearer rewording is needed. A better idea might be that, instead of measuring the effect of product types on purchase intention from a socially responsible company with the items, consumers might be asked to consider a convenience good producer while answering the remaining statements and then, the same statements might be asked again but this time considering a shopping good producer.

Similar results were also achieved in questionnaire two, in which items were measured with interval scale. As can be observed from Table VI, there is again a problem with dimension 4Ps. The source of this problem is again the same items (q9b and q15b) and the deletion of these items increases reliability coefficient from 0.628 to 0.809. In the remaining two dimensions – cause and trust – there was no need to delete any of the items.

TABLE VI
ASSESSMENT OF THE RELIABILITY ANALYSIS OF QUESTIONNAIRE 2
(INTERVAL SCALE)

Dimension Name	Reliability Before Deletions	Reliability After Deletions
4Ps	0.628	0.809
Cause	0.669	0.669
Trust	0.798	0.798

G. Assessment of Construct Validity

Obviously it is crucial for a researcher to assess how fully his/her scale measures what it intends to measure, and therefore, construct validity is taken as a very critical concern. Previously the face validity of conditions for purchase intention from a socially responsible company scale was already assessed. However, considering only that face validity really measures what a scale aims to measure is totally wrong, since face validity is weak evidence because it is essentially a subjective judgment call [31]. Therefore, the appraisal of construct validity is a better estimate of accuracy of the conclusion that an operationalization precisely reflects its construct. One of the widely accepted methods to assess construct validity is the usage of Multitrait-Multimethod Matrix (hereafter labeled MTMM) [32]. In this matrix, zero order correlations between different traits are calculated for each of the traits when they are measured by different methods [32].

This study also employs MTMM for the assessment of the construct validity of the conditions for purchase intention from a socially responsible company scale. With the purpose of constructing MTMM, data was collected to measure the traits (4Ps, cause and trust) with two different methods (ratio and interval). Internal reliability was assessed by the application of Cronbach's Alpha method, whereas the correlations between traits and methods were appraised by the usage of Pearson Correlation method. Table VII displays the MTMM.

According to [32] there are five basic rules for the assessment of construct validity through MTMM. The first rule is that, coefficients in the reliability diagonal should consistently be the highest in the matrix. However, considering Table VII, this rule is partially violated in this study, since the reliability coefficient of dimension "cause" is 0.63 in method 1 and 0.67 in method 2. Even though an alpha of 0.6 is sufficient at the early stages of research [29], the correlation of the trait of "cause" between two methods (0.75) is higher than the correlation within itself.

TABLE VII
MULTITRAIT-MULTIMETHOD MATRIX

	Method 1 (Ratio)			Method 2 (Interval)		
	4Ps	Cause	Trust	4Ps	Cause	Trust
Method 1 (Ratio)	4Ps (0.84)	Cause 0.26 (0.63)	Trust 0.40* (0.75)			
Method 2 (Interval)	4Ps 0.79**	Cause 0.05 (0.75**)	Trust 0.23 (0.59**)	4Ps (0.80)	Cause 0.28 (0.67)	Trust 0.51** (0.79)

** : Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* : Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

----- Heterotrait heteromethod triangles

_____ Heterotrait monomethod triangles

The values in parentheses form the reliability diagonal

The values in shaded numbers form the validity diagonal

The second principle is that coefficients in the validity diagonals should be significantly different from zero and high enough to warrant further investigation. Fortunately, this principle is realized, since the correlation coefficients in the validity diagonals are significantly different from zero. However, for the "trust" dimension correlation coefficient may not be considered high enough for further investigation, even though it is almost 0.6. Still, it can be concluded that the requirement for convergent validity is met.

The third principle states that a validity coefficient should be higher than values lying in its column and row in the same heteromethod block. Again, this requirement is also met since all the coefficients in the validity diagonal (0.79, 0.75, and 0.59) are higher than the values lying in the same column and row.

The fourth rule requires that a validity coefficient be higher than all coefficients in the heterotrait-monomethod blocks. Since all coefficients in the heterotrait-monomethod blocks are lower than values in validity diagonals, this requirement is also realized.

Finally, the fifth principle is that the same pattern of trait interrelationship should be seen in all triangles.

As for the final criterion, the same pattern of trait interrelationship should be observed in all of the heterotrait triangles of both the monomethod and heteromethod blocks. Unfortunately this criterion is partly supported because there is no similar pattern between all triangles.

Even though there is a problem with the realization of the first and the fifth principle, all other requirements are met. Therefore, it can be concluded that the CIPISRC scale has construct validity to some extent.

V. CONCLUSION

In order to explore the conditions that socially responsible companies need to fulfill to increase their sales, this study is designed in four parts. The first part includes the literature review with the aim of extracting dimensions that form the purchase intention from a socially responsible company. Then, four focus groups are conducted to back up the

conceptualization of company-specific conditions that consumers seek in order to prefer socially responsible companies and to generate additional dimensions or elements, if they exist. The findings that emerged from the focus groups confirm the dimensions stated in literature and furthermore, one new dimension and additional elements for the remaining dimensions are generated. With the overall dimensions and elements, 18 items were developed and two questionnaires – one with ratio, the other with interval scales – were prepared. After assessing the face validity and inter-judge reliability of the questionnaires, a sample of 38 respondents was formed by using convenience and snowball sampling methods. With the obtained data, construct validity of the scale was assessed by forming Multitrait-Multimethod Matrix. Even though some of the criteria of MTMM were not met, the scale could still be assumed to have construct validity to some extent.

One of the limitations of this study is the time break between the two questionnaires being collected. Due to time constraints, the second questionnaire was sent to the respondents ten days after the first implementation. Since the time break between two measurements should be at least two weeks apart [33], an interval of ten days is considered short. Another limitation is the size of the samples. For further research it is suggested that these limitations are eliminated so that a more coherent scale can be developed.

APPENDIX

Questionnaire:

Dear respondent,

Assume there is a company that operates in the consumer goods market. This company is a socially responsible company that fulfills its economic responsibility (being profitable), legal responsibility (obeying the rules, regulations and laws), ethical responsibility (embracing those standards, norms or expectations that reflect a concern for what consumers, employees, shareholders, and the community regard as fair, just, or in keeping with the respect or the protection of shareholders' moral rights). In addition to fulfilling these responsibilities, the company also undertakes a cause-related marketing program in which some portion of its revenue generated from the sale of its product goes to the support of a certain cause.

Below are some statements related to consumers' purchase intention from a socially respondent company. Please evaluate each statement considering the information provided about a company above and assign a score between 0-100 to each of the following. Please keep in mind that all statements start with "I will purchase from that company..."

Statement	0-100
1) ... as long as the money I spend for the product really goes to the cause	
2) ...even the price of the product is not similar to those of other brands	
3) ... as long as the brand is the one I	

know	
4) ... as long as its product has equal convenience with those of others	
5) ...even the company has bad past behavior (illegal operations, child labor, etc.) in the past	
6) ... as long as its product features are the same with those of other brands	
7) ... as long as the cause it supports is important to me	
8) ... as long as the company is a large size company	
9) ...even the company undertakes CSR just for profit	
10) ... as long as the product it sells is a convenience good	
11) ... as long as I trust the company	
12) ... as long as the consequences of the company's support is announced to the public	
13) ... even the company is not the one I know	
14) ... as long as the company is audited for its socially responsible undertakings	
15) ... as long as the product it sells is a shopping good	
16) ...even the support of the company to the cause is low	
17) ... as long as the company undertakes CSR activities for a long time	
18) ... as long as the company communicates its support to the cause by tools other than advertisements	

Please indicate your,

Name & Surname:

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